

The Existence of the Anisotropy of the Speed of Light.

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Abstract.

The extreme majority of scientists believe that there is isotropy of the speed of light, and that the special and general relativity are correct.

I disagree, and on this paper I will demonstrate why there is anisotropy of the speed of light! If, contrary to the belief of the scientific community, there is actually anisotropy of the speed of light, this is a fundamental change on our ideas about reality, physics and the universe!

At the beginning of the paper, I will present the findings of some experiments and what they actually show, which is extremely important, because I will use these findings to prove the existence of the anisotropy of the speed of light.

Afterwards I will focus on the terms isotropy and anisotropy and analyze what do they mean regarding speed, using two examples with moving balls and protons.

Also, I will explain that we regard the simultaneous emission of many photons towards all directions by a light source, as one event, as the emission of one light wave!!!

Then, I will use an example with sources emitting photons to demonstrate why there is anisotropy of the speed of light!!!

I will also use an example where I will explain that the one-way speed of light is not always the same, only the two-way speed is the same!

Also very important, is my idea about the changes in the energy of the photons, which is a lot different than the ideas of the scientific community, and basically I will explain that the energy on the photons changes for the same reason that the energy on other particles changes, and that reason is different speed!!!

Then, I will use another example regarding the anisotropy of the speed of light, with sources emitting both photons and protons, and on the example we will have the same conclusions for both protons and photons, which is that for both protons and photons there is anisotropy of the speeds relative to their sources!!!

Extremely important is also the example using many light sources where I will demonstrate that the anisotropy of the speed of light is what usually occurs!

It is the normality on the universe!!!

At the end I will show why the "Sagnac effect" confirms the occurrence of the anisotropy.

Introduction.

The extreme majority of scientists believe there is isotropy of the speed of light, and that the special and general relativity are correct.

I disagree, and next I will demonstrate why there is anisotropy of the speed of light!

If, contrary to the belief of the scientific community, there is actually anisotropy of the speed of light, this is a fundamental change on our ideas about reality!

At the beginning I will present the findings of some experiments, and what they actually show, which is extremely important, because I will use these findings to prove the existence of the anisotropy of the speed of light.

Afterwards I will focus on the terms isotropy and anisotropy and analyze what do they mean, using two examples with moving balls and protons.

When we use the terms **isotropy** & **anisotropy** we refer to differences dependent on direction, and specifically if we refer to anisotropy of speeds we mean that towards different directions we have different speeds.

Also, I will explain that we regard the simultaneous emission of many photons towards all directions by a light source, as one event, as the emission of one light wave!!!

Then, I will use an example with two sources emitting photons to demonstrate why there is anisotropy of the speed of light!!!

I will also use an example where I will show that the one-way speed of light is not always the same, only the two-way speed is the same.

Also very important, is my idea about the changes in the energy of the photons, which is a lot different than the ideas of the scientific community, and basically I will explain that the energy on the photons changes for the same reason that the energy on other particles changes, and that reason is different speed!!!

Then, on another important example, I will use sources emitting both photons and protons, and on the example we will have the same conclusions for both protons and photons, which is that for both protons and photons there is anisotropy of the speeds relative to their sources!!!

Extremely important is also the example using many light sources where I will demonstrate that the anisotropy of the speed of light is what usually occurs.

It is the normality on the universe!!!

At the end I will show why the "Sagnac effect" confirms the existence of the anisotropy.

The findings of some experiments.

Experiments have shown that the motion of the photons(light) does not depend on the motion of the source of the light at the moment of the emission.

There are many experiments confirming this, and one of them was conducted in 1964 by Torsten Alvager and his colleagues.

From the results of the experiments that are conducted, we have concluded that the motion of the source of the light does not affect the motion of the photons that the source will emit, like the **figure 1** example shows.

In the **figure 1** I have tried to depict in one picture what the findings of the experiments are showing, which is that the speed of a photon is always the same regardless of the motion of its source.

For every photon that it is emitted by the source on the **figure 1** example, we will find that it moves always at the same speed while travelling from the one human to the other, regardless of the motion of the source at the moment of the emission.

Figure 1. A photon will always make the same motion and will move from the one human to the other always at the same speed, regardless of the motion of the light source at the moment of the emission.

What the findings of the experiments are actually showing is what we will see on the example in the [figures 2 & 3](#).

Figure 2,a. The **light source B** is moving towards the **light source A** with a direction towards the humans.

Suppose that there are two humans stationary on the surface of the Earth (**figure 2,a**), and a source of light, the **light source A**, is also stationary on the surface of the Earth, and they are arranged like we see in the **figure 2,a**.

Another source of light, the **light source B**, is moving towards the **light source A** and the two humans, as we see in the **figure 2,a**.

When the **light source B** is next to the **light source A** (as we see in the **figure 2**), each light source will emit a photon with a direction towards the two humans.

The **light source A** will emit the **photon A**, and the **light source B** will emit (**figure 3**) the **photon B**.

Figure 2. When the **light source B** is next to the **light source A**, both sources will emit a photon towards the humans.

The **photons A & B** which are emitted by the **light sources A & B** will move at the same speed, and basically we can say that the two photons will always be the one next to the other, practically forming a group(or pair) of photons, while traveling towards the two humans, as we see in the **figure 3!!!!**

The **light sources A & B** will not stay next to each other because they are in relative motion with each other, and the one source will be closer to the photons (**figure 3**) that are moving away.

The two light sources were next to each other only when they emitted the photons (**figure 2**).

Figure 3. The two photons which are emitted by the two light sources will move exactly the same, practically forming a group of photons.

What we see in the **figure 3** we will use it to reveal the anisotropy of the speed of light!!!
On the example in the **figures 2 & 3** we see that the two photons which are emitted by the two sources will make the exact same motion, regardless of the motion of their sources, practically moving as a group of photons, being always next to each other as they are moving away from the sources!!!

The fact that the photons will make the same motion regardless of the motion of the source, is actually the reason why there is anisotropy!!!!

But, in order for the anisotropy to be revealed, we must use an example with the sources emitting photons towards two opposite directions!!!!!!

On the example in the **figure 3** it's not so easy to see the anisotropy of the speed of light. The anisotropy of the speed of light is revealed when the sources emit light towards two opposites direction, so next we will find why what we see in the **figure 3** leads to the acceptance that there is anisotropy of the speed of light!!!!!!!!!!

Before proceeding, let's see what do we mean when we talk about **anisotropy** of speeds.

When we use the terms **isotropy & anisotropy** we refer to differences dependent on direction, and specifically if we refer to anisotropy of speeds we mean that towards different directions we have different speeds.

Next I will present some examples where I will use the terms "**isotropy**" & "**anisotropy**" but I will also use the terms "**equality**" & "**inequality**" because I will talk about differences on relative speeds towards the same direction.

Let's see an example with balls.

Suppose that I have two small balls in my right hand.

At some point I move my hand and I throw the balls away, and the two balls are moving on the ground **towards the same direction**.

If the balls are always at the same distance from me as they are moving away, we will say that **the two balls have the same speed relative to me**, and this we can call it **equality** of the speeds of the balls relative to me!!!

On the contrary, if the balls are always **not** at the same distance from me as they are moving away, and if the one ball increases the distance from me at a greater rate than the other ball, we will say that **the two balls do not have the same speed relative to me**, and this we can call it **inequality** of the speeds of the balls relative to me!!!!

Next imagine a little different situation.

Suppose that I have one ball on each hand, and I move my hands simultaneously and I throw the balls **towards different directions**.

If the balls are always at the same distance from me as they are moving away, we will say that **the two balls have the same speed relative to me**, and this we can call it **equality** of the speeds of the balls relative to me, or we can call it **isotropy** of the speeds of the balls relative to me because we refer to different directions!!!

On the contrary, if the balls are always **not** at the same distance from me as they are moving away, and if the one ball increases the distance from me at a greater rate than the other ball, we will say that **the two balls do not have the same speed relative to me**, and this we can call it **inequality** of the speeds of the balls relative to me, or we can call it **anisotropy** of the speeds of the balls relative to me because we refer to different directions!!!!

And of course this is not only the case with balls!!!

The same applies to the motion of everything!!!

If we use protons or photons instead of balls our conclusions will be the same!!!

For example, suppose that in a particle accelerator a source emits simultaneously two **protons**.

If the source emits the protons **towards the same direction** and they are **not at the same distance from the source** as they are moving away, and if the one proton increases the distance from the source at a greater rate than the other proton, we will say that **the protons don't have the same speed relative to the source**, and we will say that there is **inequality** of the speeds of the protons relative to the source!!!

Now, if the protons are emitted **towards different directions** and they are always **not at the same distance from the source** as they are moving away, and if the one proton increases the distance from the source at a greater rate than the other proton, again we will say that **the two protons do not have the same speed relative to the source**, and this we can call it **inequality** of the speeds of the protons relative to the source, or we can call it **anisotropy** of the speeds of the protons relative to the source because we refer to different directions!!!

And of course, we are talking about the **one-way speed!!!**

When we are referring to the relative speed between two objects, any objects, we are referring to the **one-way relative speed!!!**

For example, when we are referring to the relative speed between two cars, we are referring to the **one-way relative speed**, and the same applies for the speed of particles!

The **figure A** example will help us understand.

Suppose that a human has one small ball in his right hand and two small balls in his left hand. At some point the human moves his hands and throws simultaneously the three balls which are moving on the ground.

The right hand throws the one ball towards one direction and the left hand throws the two other balls towards the opposite direction.

So, one ball is moving towards one direction(ball A) and the other two balls(balls B & C) are moving towards the opposite direction, like we see on the **figure A**.

Suppose that as the balls are moving away from the human, the distance between the human and the **ball A** is always the same with the distance between the human and the **ball B**, but the distance between the human and the **ball C** is always larger than the other balls, and the **ball C** increases the distance from the human at a greater rate than the other balls(**figure A**).

Our conclusions are the following:

- The relative speed between the human and the **ball A** is the same with the relative speed between the human and the **ball B**, because the two balls are always at the same distance away from the human, and this we will call it **isotropy/equality of the relative speeds!!!**
- The relative speed between the human and the **ball C** is **larger** than the relative speed between the human and the **ball A**, because the **ball C** is always farther away from the human, and this we will call it **anisotropy/inequality of the relative speeds!!!**
- The relative speed between the human and the **ball C** is **larger** than the relative speed between the human and the **ball B**, because the **ball C** is always farther away from the human, and this we will call it **inequality of the relative speeds!!!**

Figure A. The three balls have left the human simultaneously, and as they are moving away, the ball C is farther away from the human. This means that the relative speed between the human and the ball C is larger than the relative speed between the human and the balls A & B. The balls A & B are at the same distance from the human as they are moving away, therefore we will say that the balls A & B have the same speed relative to the human.

Next let's see an example similar with the previous, but now we will have a source that emits **protons**(figure B), and we will have the same conclusions with the previous example.

Suppose that on a particle accelerator there is a source/emitter that emits **protons**.

At some point the source emits simultaneously three **protons**.

Two protons are moving towards the same direction(protons B & C) and one proton(proton A) is moving towards the opposite direction, as we see on the **figure B**.

Suppose that as the protons are moving away from the source/emitter, the distance between the emitter and the **proton A** is always the same with the distance between the emitter and the **proton B**, but the distance between the source/emitter and the **proton C** is always larger than the other protons, and the **proton C** increases the distance from the emitter at a greater rate than the other protons(**figure B**).

Our conclusions are the following:

- The relative speed between the source/emitter and the **proton A** is the same with the relative speed between the source/emitter and the **proton B**, because the two protons are always at the same distance away from the source/emitter, and this we will call it **isotropy/equality** of the relative speeds!!!

- The relative speed between the emitter and the **proton C** is **larger** than the relative speed between the emitter and the **proton A**, because the **proton C** is always farther away from the emitter, and this we will call it **anisotropy/inequality of the relative speeds!!!**
- The relative speed between the emitter and the **proton C** is **larger** than the relative speed between the emitter and the **proton B**, because the **proton C** is always farther away from the emitter, and this we will call it **inequality of the relative speeds!!!**

Figure B. The source/emitter emits the three protons simultaneously, and as the three protons are moving away, the proton C is farther away from the emitter. This means that the relative speed between the source/emitter and the proton C is larger than the relative speed between the source/emitter and the protons A & B. The protons A & B are at the same distance from the emitter as they are moving away, therefore we will say that the protons A & B have the same speed relative to the emitter.

I have used the term "simultaneously" when referring to a human throwing simultaneously some balls and a source emitting simultaneously some protons.

Do not confuse this with the "relativity of simultaneity"!!!

The "relativity of simultaneity" is about the order of events that occur at different locations!!!

The order of events that occur at different locations may not be the same for humans that are at different locations.

The order of events that occur at one location is the same for every human regardless of his location or his motion!!!

When, for example, I'm saying that a source emits simultaneously two protons towards two opposite directions, those two emissions of the two protons occur at the same location by the same source!!!

Let's see an example that will help us understand:

Suppose that I have two balls, one on each of my hands, and I want to throw them away!!!

On my head I have a hat that has two light bulbs, one red and one blue.

When I will throw the ball that I have on my right hand, the red light bulb will be switched on.

When I will throw the ball that I have on my left hand, the blue light bulb will be switched on.

With that system, anyone who is far away from me and cannot clearly see my moves can be informed about when I will throw each ball!!!

Suppose that there are two humans far away from me at opposite directions relative to me, and they are at such distance where they cannot clearly see my moves!!!

So, in order for the humans to be informed about when I will throw the balls, they will use the two light bulbs that I have on my hat.

At some point I throw the two balls and the two lights are switched on, and according to me I have thrown them simultaneously!!!

But not only according to me, also the two humans will say that I threw them simultaneously, because both they will see that the two light bulbs have switched on simultaneously, regardless if they are at different locations and regardless of their motion relative to me!!!

Now, if the two humans are close to me and can see my hands moving, both humans will see that my two hands are moving simultaneously and will see the two balls leaving me simultaneously!!!

Next let's see a situation where two balls are hitting me simultaneously:

Suppose that two fast moving balls are flying towards me, one towards my right side and one towards my left side.

Two humans are far away from me at opposite directions and watching me.

When the one ball will hit me on my right side I will raise my right hand and when the other ball hits me on my left side I will raise my left hand.

So, the two balls hit me and I raise my hands.

According to me, the two balls hit me simultaneously and I will simultaneously raise my two hands!!!

If I say that two balls will hit me simultaneously, can anyone argue that they have not hit me simultaneously???

Of course not!!!

Each of the two humans that are watching me from different locations will see my two hands raised simultaneously, and so they will also say that the two balls will hit me simultaneously!

If the two humans are close to me and able to see the balls while they are moving, they will both see that the two balls will hit my body simultaneously!!!

So, the two balls are hitting me simultaneously according to me, but also according to everyone else!!!

An important realisation!!!

We refer to the light as "photons" and also as "light wave".

Imagine that we have a light bulb that can emit light/photons towards all directions, and currently is switched-off.

At some point the light bulb is switched-on.

When the light bulb is switched-on and starting to emit light/photons towards all directions, it is created the first wavefront that propagates away from the light bulb.

The only thing that we can say about the photons that consist the first wavefront is that they all are emitted simultaneously!!!

We have an emission of many(thousands-millions-billions etc.) photons towards all directions by the light bulb, and we can see them as a number of photons or as one light wave, because all these photons are emitted simultaneously by the source and are creating one wave!!!

So, we can say that the light bulb emits photons simultaneously towards all directions or we can say that the light bulb emits a light wave towards all directions, and **of course this is one emission of one light wave, meaning that we regard the simultaneous emission of many photons towards all directions as ONE EVENT, as an emission of one light wave!!**

What we have seen on the **figures A & B** where we use balls and protons we will compare it with what we will see on the **figures 5-B & 5-Z** where we will use photons, and we will have the same conclusions regarding the relative speeds.

Let's see why there is anisotropy of the speed of light.

Suppose that somewhere(anywhere, it doesn't matter where) there are two sources of light that are moving towards each other(**figure 4,a**).

We call these sources **light source A & light source B**.

The sources currently do not emit light.

At some point the **light sources A & B** are next to each other(**figure 4**).

When the **light sources A & B** are the one next to the other(**figure 4**), each source will emit two photons, one photon towards the direction from where the other source is coming, and the other photon towards the direction that the other source is going.

So practically the two sources will emit photons towards the same two opposite directions.

After the emission of the photons the sources are moving away from each other because their relative motion continues.

Figure 4,a. Two light sources are moving towards each other.

Figure 4. When the two light sources are next to each other they will emit the photons.

So, when the two sources are next to each other (figure 4), each source will emit simultaneously two photons!!!

The **light source A** emits the **photons A & C** and the **light source B (figure 5-A)** emits the **photons B & D**.

The **photons A & B** are moving towards the one direction and the **photons C & D** are moving towards the other direction, like we see in the **figure 5-A**.

The **photons A & B** will move exactly the same, and basically we can say that they will always be the one next to the other, practically forming a group of photons, and also the **photons C & D** will move exactly the same, meaning that they will always be the one next to the other, practically forming another group of photons, like we see in the **figure 5-A!**

But, the light sources A & B will not stay next to each other (figure 5-A)!!!!

The light sources A & B were the one next to the other (figure 4) when they emitted the photons, but afterwards they are moving away from each other!!!!

So, there are two groups of photons, the **group A & B** and the **group C & D (figure 5-A)** which are moving away from the two sources, and also there are the **light sources A & B** which are moving away from each other, and there are the following two possibilities:

- First possibility: Only the one of the sources can be exactly between the two groups of photons (**figures 5-A & 5-B**).

- Second possibility: Both sources will not be exactly between the two groups of photons (**figure 5-Z**).

The important realisation is that there cannot be both the **light source A** and the **light source B** exactly between the two moving groups of photons, because the two sources are moving away from each other after the emission of the photons!!!

Only the one of the two light sources can be exactly between the two groups of photons, and consequently, only the one light source can have the same distance from the two groups of photons!!!!

So, the one possibility is that only the one of the sources can be exactly between the two groups of photons (**figure 5-B**), and **the other possibility is that both the light source A and the light source B will not be exactly between** the two groups of photons, like we see in the **figure 5-Z!!!**

But, the possibility for both the light source A and the light source B to be located exactly between the two groups of photons, simply does not exist!!!

The **figures 5-A & 5-B** present the case where the one of the two light sources is exactly between the two groups of photons.

This is the one possibility, and the other possibility is that both the **light source A** and the **light source B** will not be exactly between the two groups of photons, and a situation like this is depicted in the **figure 5-Z!!!!**

In the vast majority of the cases what is happening is what the figure 5-Z depicts, meaning that both light sources will not be exactly between the two groups of photons!!!

On the **figures 5-A & 5-B** i have intentionally placed the one of the two light sources exactly between the two groups of photons, in order to show that if the one source is exactly between the two groups of photons, the other light source cannot be exactly between the two groups of photons!!!!

Figure 5-A. There are two groups of photons moving away from the sources, the **group A & B** and the **group C & D**.

Due to the fact that the **light sources A & B** are moving away from each other after the emission of the photons, there cannot be both sources exactly between the two groups of photons.

On the example that I present in the **figures 5-A & 5-B**, the **light source A** is exactly between the two moving groups of photons, and consequently the **light source B** is not, because the **light source B** is moving away from the **light source A** after the emission of the photons!!! The two groups(or pairs) of photons are emitted/created when the **light sources A & B** were next to each other.

As the photons are moving away from the sources, the sources are moving away from each other, and due to that fact there cannot be both light sources exactly between the two groups of photons!!!

If the **light source A** is exactly between the two groups of photons, this means that the two groups of photons are always at the same distance away from the **light source A**(**figure 5-B**), and this also means that the relative speed between the **photons A & B** and the **light source A** is the same with the relative speed between the **photons C & D** and the **light source A**!!!

This is something that is happening since the emission of the photons!!!

But if this is the case for the light source A, it could not also be the case for the light source B because the **light source B** is not exactly between the two groups of photons due to the fact that is moving away from the **light source A** after the emission of photons, meaning that the one group of photons is always closer to the **light source B** than the other group, and on the **figures 5-A & 5-B** we see that the **photons A & B** are closer to the **light source B** than the **photons C & D**, and this is happening since the emission of the photons which occurred when the sources were next to each other!!!

Therefore, regarding the **light source B** there is anisotropy of the speed of light, and specifically on the example that I present in the **figures 5-A & 5-B**, the relative speed between the **photons A & B** and the **light source B** is smaller than the relative speed between the **photons C & D** and the **light source B**, because since the emission of the photons, the **photons A & B** are always closer to the **light source B** than the **photons C & D**! So, if the relative speed between the **photons A & B** and the **light source A** is the same with the relative speed between the **photons C & D** and the **light source A**, due to the fact the light source B is in relative motion with the light source A, the relative speed between the **photons A & B** and the **light source B** is **different** than the relative speed between the **photons C & D** and the **light source B**!!!

Figure 5-B. The figure 5-B is the same with the figure 5-A, but additionally shows the distances. The **distance A** is the same with the **distance C**, but the distance B is smaller than the distance D, which means that the **photons A & B** are closer to the **light source B** and the **photons C & D** are farther away from the **light source B**.

We can see the motion of the photons as groups moving relative to the sources or we can focus on the relative motion between a source and the individual photons that the source emits!!! The **photons A & C** are emitted by the **light source A** when the light source B was next to it, and as they are moving away from the source, the **photons A & C** are always at the same distance away from the **light source A** (distance A equal to distance C, **figure 5-B**) because the source is exactly between them, which means that we must say that the relative speed between the **photon A** and the **light source A** is the same with the relative speed between the **photon C** and the **light source A**, which means that we must say that there is isotropy of the speed of light relative to this source!!!!

But, is not happening the same for the light source B!!!!

The **photons B & D** are emitted by the **light source B** when the light source A was next to it, and as they are moving away from the source, the **photons B & D** are always not at the same distance away from the **light source B**(distance B not equal to distance D, **figure 5-B**) because the **light source B** is not exactly between the photons B & D, which means that we must say that the relative speed between the **photon B** and the **light source B** is different than the relative speed between the **photon D** and the **light source B**!!!!

Specifically on my example in the **figures 5-A & 5-B**, the **photon B** is always closer to the **light source B** than the **photon D**(distance B smaller than the distance D), which means that we must say that the relative speed between the **photon B** and the **light source B** is smaller than the relative speed between the **photon D** and the **light source B**!!!!

Of course this means that there is anisotropy of the speed of light relative to the **light source B**!!!

On the example that is depicted in the **figures 5-A & 5-B**, the **photons B & D** are emitted by the **light source B**, but the **photons B & D** are having the same speed relative to the **light source A** and not relative to their own source!!!!!!!!!!!!

The **photons B & D** are emitted by the **light source B**, but we must say that the **photons B & D** have the same speed relative to the **light source A**, because since their emission/creation the **photons B & D** are always at the same distance away from the **light source A**, and we must say that the **photons B & D** don't have the same speed relative to the **light source B** which is their source, because since their emission/creation the **photons B & D** are always not at the same distance away from the **light source B**!!!!!!

Meaning that there is a situation where the **light source B** emits the **photons B & D**, but there is anisotropy of the speed of the **photons B & D** relative to their source, and there is isotropy of the speed of the **photons B & D** relative to the **light source A** which is not their source!!!

If we compare the **figures A & B** with the **figures 5-B & 5-Z** we see that they are similar and we reach the same conclusions regarding the relative speeds regardless if we have balls, protons or photons!!!

And something else very important:

If we say that the time on the **light source B** is slower(or faster) than the time on the **light source A**, that fact makes no difference, because the thing that matters is that fact that the **light source B** emits **simultaneously** the **photons B & D**, but since their emission these photons are not at the same distance away from the source(figures 5-A, 5-B), and this is regardless of how fast or slow the time on the light source B is running!!!!!!

On the other hand, the **light source A** also emits **simultaneously** the **photons A & C**, but these photons are always at the same distance away from the source, and it doesn't matter how fast or slow the time on the source is running!!!

On the specific example that we see in the **figure 5-B** there is anisotropy of the speed of light only relative to the one source(the light source B), but in the case where both light sources are not exactly between the two groups of photons, like we see in the **figure 5-Z**, then there is anisotropy of the speed of light for both light sources!!!!!!

In the vast majority of the cases what is happening is what the **figure 5-Z** depicts, meaning that in the vast majority of the cases will be anisotropy of the speed of light for both light sources!!!

The important realisation is that the possibility to have isotropy of the speed of light for both the **light source A** and the **light source B** does not exist, because there cannot be both light sources exactly between the two groups of photons, due to the fact that the two sources are moving away from each other after the emission of the photons!!!!

Figure 5-Z. Presents a situation where both light sources are not exactly between the two groups of photons, meaning that **there is anisotropy of the speed of light for both sources.** The **Distance C** is smaller than the **Distance A** & the **Distance B** is smaller than the **Distance D**.

As you have probably understand so far, i'm talking about the one-way speed of light!!!!

But wait a moment, when we are talking about the speed of an object relative to another object, regardless if these objects are photons, electrons, protons, cars, planets or anything else, we are referring to the one-way relative speed!!!

The "one-way speed" is what we call "SPEED"!!!

When we are talking about the relative speed between two cars, we are talking about the one-way relative speed, and when we are talking about the relative speed between fast moving muons and the Earth, we are also talking about the one-way relative speed!!!

What about the two-way speed of light, one may ask???

On the example in the **figure 5-Z** we see that the one-way speed of light on the two opposite directions is not the same for both light sources, because for both sources the photons emitted towards the two opposite directions are not at the same distance!!!

But even though this will happen, the two-way speed of light on the two opposite directions will be the same, and this is something that will happen to both sources!!!!

In order to see how this is happening we have to see the next example/explanation!!!

On the next example I will use light waves instead of photons.

Figure M. The source emits light towards two opposite directions, and if we compare the distances between the source and the light waves on the two directions we will see that the distance A is twice the distance B.

For the next example/explanation I will use a hypothetical case where a source emits light towards two opposite directions, and as the light is moving away from the source, the light that is moving towards the one direction is at twice the distance away from the source compared to the distance between the source and the light moving towards the other direction!!!

The **figure M** depicts a situation like this.

Imagine that our light source is a normal light bulb which can emit simultaneously light towards all directions, but we have put covers around it in specific places so that the light that it emits is not spreading towards all directions, but instead is spreading only towards two opposite directions.

Let's see the example.

We have the light source(light bulb) that we talk about earlier and we also have two reflectors(mirrors) in our possession, the reflectors 1 & 2.

We place the source exactly between the two reflectors, which means that the two reflectors are at the same distance from the source.

Light source and reflectors are stationary relative to each other.

At some point we switch-on the light source and it starts to emit light towards the two opposite directions where the reflectors are placed.

The **figure N,1** depicts this moment, meaning the moment of the emission of light by the source(light bulb), and we see the two light waves just starting to move away from the source.

Figure N, 1. The moment of the emission of light by the source.

Two light waves starting to move away from the source and towards the two reflectors.

As I have said earlier, the light wave that is moving towards the one direction is at twice the distance away from the source compared to the distance between the source and the light wave moving towards the opposite direction!!!

Specifically, the light wave that is moving with a direction towards the reflector 1 is the one that is at twice the distance away from the source compared to the distance between the source and the light wave moving towards the reflector 2(**figure N, 2**).

Since the reflectors are stationary relative to the light source, this ratio of motions of the light waves relative to the source is also the same relative to the reflectors!!!

So, it is very important to realise that we have a situation where relative to the source and the reflectors, the light wave moving with a direction from the reflector 2 towards the reflector 1 is making twice the distance that the light wave moving with a direction from the reflector 1 to the reflector 2 is making(**figure N, 2**)!!!

This is very important to realise and we will need it again!!!

(This is the motion of the light relative to the specific source and reflectors, and only relative to them or any other object stationary relative to them.)

A very important note:

If the light wave that is moving towards the reflector 2 reflect somewhere and start to move towards the opposite direction meaning towards the reflector 1, it will make similar motion with the other light wave because they will be moving towards the same direction!!!

It's the direction of motion of the light that determines towards which direction the motion will be larger!!!

(I'm talking about the motion of the light waves relative to the source and the reflectors.)

If both light waves reflect somewhere and their directions of motion are reversed, the thing that will also be reversed is which light wave will make larger motion relative to the source and the reflectors, because the fact that determines which light wave makes the larger motion is the direction of motion of the wave, and the light wave moving with a direction from the reflector 2 towards the reflector 1 will make twice the distance that the light wave moving with a direction from the reflector 1 to the reflector 2 is making.

At the moment that the one light wave have reach the reflector 1 and reflect on it, the other light wave will be at half the distance between the source and the reflector 2(**figure N, 3**).

The light wave that is reflected to the reflector 1 will start to move towards the source and the reflector 2, meaning that **now the two light waves are moving towards the same direction**, and due to that fact the two light waves will make similar motion relative to the source and the reflectors(from **figure N,3** to **figure N,4**).

So, when the other light wave reach the reflector 2 and reflect on it, the other light wave will be exactly at half the distance between the reflector 1 and the light source on its journey back to the source(**figure N, 4**)!!!

Figure N, 3. When the one light wave is reflected to the reflector 1 the other light wave is at half the distance between the source and the reflector 2.

Figure N, 4. When the one light wave is reflected to the reflector 2 the other light wave is at half the distance between the reflector 1 and the source.

Now, the light wave that is reflected to the reflector 2 will move towards the opposite direction, meaning that it will move towards the reflector 1 (**figure N,5**), and now we have again two light waves moving towards opposite directions as we were having earlier, but **now the direction of motion of the light waves is reversed and so is their motion relative to the source and the reflectors**.

As I have said earlier, the thing that determines the extent of the motion of the light waves relative to the source and the reflectors is the direction of motion, and the light wave that has direction of motion from the reflector 2 towards the reflector 1 will make twice the distance that the light wave moving from the reflector 1 towards the reflector 2 will make!!!

So now, the light wave that is reflected to the reflector 2 is moving towards the reflector 1 (and the source), meaning that now this light wave will make twice the distance that the other light wave is making because the other light wave is moving from the reflector 1 towards the reflector 2 (and the source) after its reflection to the reflector 1 (**figures N, 5 & N, 6**)!!!

The final result will be that the two light waves will return to the source simultaneously, as we can see on the **figure N, 6**!!!

Figure N, 5

Figure N, 6

So, what do we have on this example/experiment???

We have a source and two reflectors stationary at the same distance away from the source.

The source emits simultaneously (according to the source) the two light waves towards the two reflectors, and the two light waves will return simultaneously to the source.

Since the light waves are emitted simultaneously by the source, since they have to travel the same distance and since they will return simultaneously, the source (a human on the source) thinks that the speed of the two light waves relative to the source was the same, but **the one-way speed of light was not the same**, only the two-way speed was the same!!!

The "Sagnac effect" is the result of the one-way anisotropy of the speed of light!!!

So, we see that even though the one-way speed of light relative to the source is different we end up with the same two-way relative speed for the two opposite directions!!!

We don't actually need all the figures in order to describe what happens. Basically there are three steps, and we see them in the **figures N,3 - N,4 & N,6** that we see again below.

Figure N, 3. Light wave reflecting to the reflector 1.

Figure N, 4. Light wave reflecting to the reflector 2.

Figure N, 6. The two light waves returning to the source.

On this example(**figures N,3 - N,4 - N,6**) the one light wave makes 50 percent of the distance (relative to the source) that the light wave moving towards the opposite direction is making, but we can use whatever ratio of distances we want.

The end result always remain the same!!!

If, for example, the one light wave makes 90 percent of the distance(relative to the source) that the other light wave is making, there will be no difference on the final result.

The end result again will be that the two light waves will return to the source simultaneously, and the **figures P,3 - P,4 - P,6** present this case!!!

Figure P, 3. Light wave reflecting to the reflector 1.

Figure P, 4. Light wave reflecting to the reflector 2.

Figure P, 6. The two light waves returning to the source.

When the two light waves are moving towards the same direction (from **figures N,3 – P,3** to **figures N,4 - P,4**) they are making the same motion (the percentage that we see in the **figures N,4 - P,4**) relative to the source and the reflectors.

When both light waves have been reflected to the reflectors and their direction of motion is reversed compared to their motion prior to their reflection (from **figures N,4 - P,4** to **figures N,6 - P,6**), also their percentage of motion relative to the source and the reflectors is reversed compared to their motion prior to their reflection that we see in the **figures N,3 - P,3**.

Regarding the changes in the energy of the photons.

We talk about the wave-particle duality and we say that all matter exhibit wave-like behavior. The scientific community says that all particles, and not only photons, behave also as waves. According to the scientific community, any particle(proton, electron, etc.) has frequency and wavelength, like the photons.

The frequency & wavelength of a particle is related to the energy of the particle.

In addition to that, for all particles(photon, electron, proton, etc.) we can have changes in its energy, which for a photon we call it "blueshift" or "redshift".

Higher energy of a particle means higher frequency and shorter wavelength, which we call it "blueshift"!!!

Lower energy of a particle means lower frequency and larger wavelength, which we call it "redshift"!!!

But, according to the scientific community, there is a difference regarding the changes on the energy of photons and the changes on the energy of other particles!!!

Regarding all the other particles(protons, electrons, etc.) but not the photons, the scientific community says that the energy of a particle changes when its speed relative to us changes, meaning that also the frequency and the wavelength of the particle changes!!!

With higher relative speed the particle has higher energy, meaning higher frequency and shorter wavelength.

With lower relative speed the particle has lower energy, meaning lower frequency and larger wavelength.

But, according to the scientific community, the changes on the energy of a **photon** do not occur due to changes in relative speed, but they occur due to other reasons, because according to the scientific community the speed of light is always the same!!!!

My idea(regarding the changes in the energy of the photons).

Changes on the energy of photons occur due to changes in the relative speed between photons and observers(maybe they also occur due to other reasons)!!!

In my opinion, what happens with the other particles(**protons, electrons**, etc.) also happens with the **photons**, meaning that we detect blueshift and redshift on photons for the same reason that we detect changes in the energy on other particles, meaning that we detect changes in the energy of a photon when its speed relative to us changes, which is what happens with the other particles(protons, electrons, etc.)!!!

The scientific community believes that the one-way speed of the photons is always the same, and the redshift & blueshift on photons is not the result of different speed relative to us!!!

But this is wrong!!!

Let's say that we have a **proton** on the move in a particle accelerator.

When the **proton** collides with a detector, the higher the relative speed between the proton and the detector, the higher the energy that the detector will find, meaning that the detector will detect higher frequency & shorter wavelength on that **proton** as the speed increases!!!

The lower the speed of the **proton** relative to the detector, the lower the energy that we detect, meaning that we detect lower frequency & larger wavelength compared to what we will detect with higher speed of the proton!!!

This is the reason why we also detect changes in the energy of the **photons!!!**

If we have two identical photons moving towards two detectors but at different speeds relative to the detectors, when the photons collide with the detectors, on the case where between the **photon** and the detector the relative speed is lower the detector will find lower energy meaning lower frequency & larger wavelength(redshift), and on the case where between the **photon** and the detector the relative speed is higher the detector will find higher energy meaning higher frequency & shorter wavelength(blueshift)!!!

The different relative speed between the photons and the detectors is not caused only by different motion of the photons!!!

The motion of the detectors can be the cause of the different relative speed!!!

All the photons will make the same motion compared to each other in a specific area in space!

In order to determine the relative speed between two objects, regardless if these objects are photons, protons, detectors, cars, planets, or anything else, we focus on the state of both objects, meaning that in order to determine the relative speed between a photon and a detector, we must focus not only on what the photons are doing but also on what the detectors are doing!!!

It is a collision between two objects that are in relative motion with each other, a collision between the detector and the particle(photon, electron, proton, etc.), and **whether we consider that the particle is moving towards the detector or the detector towards the particle or both, it makes no difference!!!**

This applies to all the particles, including the photons!!!

All the protons are the same, and the reason why we find different energy during the collision between a proton and a detector is because there is different relative speed between the proton and the detector!!!

Whether we consider that the proton is moving towards the detector or the detector towards the proton it makes no difference!!!

Exactly the same applies also for the photons!!!

Specific photons that are emitted from sources through the same transition of the electrons between different energy levels, are always the same, and the reason why we find different energy during the collision between these specific photons and a detector is because there is different relative speed between the photon and the detector!!!

Whether we consider that the photon is moving towards the detector or the detector towards the photon or both, it makes no difference because all that we have is a particle and a detector in relative motion with each other!!!

(The "doppler effect" that is produced due to the relative motion between a receiver/detector and a light source that emits repeating light waves is produced through a different mechanism/process.)

A **proton** moving at high speed inside a particle accelerator will have higher energy during the collision with a detector compared to a proton that moves with lower speed, and that happens because the energy of the collision is higher due to the fact that the relative speed between the proton and the detector is higher!!!

If we have two **protons** that are moving with different speeds relative to a detector, the **proton** that moves with the lower speed will have lower energy during the collision with the detector,

meaning that it will have lower frequency & larger wavelength compared to the other **proton** that moves with higher speed and it will have higher energy during the collision with the detector!!!

The same happens with the **photons**, meaning that when the relative speed between a photon and a detector is higher, at the moment that the **photon hits the detector it will have higher energy**(blueshift) because the energy of the collision is higher due to the higher relative speed between the photon and the detector, and on that **same photon or to an identical** to that, when the relative speed between the photon and the detector is lower the detector will detect **photon with lower energy**, meaning lower frequency & larger wavelength(redshift), due to the fact that the energy of the collision between the photon and the detector is lower!!!

Idea: It seems to me that particles(photons, electrons, protons, etc.) don't actually have wavelength & frequency, but it is just something that we have attributed to them without actually having it!!!!

There is a chance that some may misunderstood what I'm saying, so, I will clarify.

Photons are emitted by electrons in atoms through specific transitions of the electrons between different energy levels!!!

The atoms of each element emit photons with specific energy that is different than the energy of photons that are emitted by the atoms of other elements.

For example, the atoms of hydrogen emit photons with different energy than the atoms of helium.

So, not all photons are the same regarding their energy at the moment of their emission by the atoms.

There are many different photons that are emitted/created by the atoms with different energies compared to each other!!!

Now, regarding the changes in the energy of photons, what i'm saying is this:

There are many different photons with different energies compared to each other, and they are emitted by the atoms with this different energy, but when photons collide with a detector we find different energy than the energy that we are expecting depending on their speed relative to the detector!!!

For example:

Suppose we have atoms of a certain element, and these atoms emit photons that are moving towards some detectors.

We expect these photons to have a specific energy, but when they will collide with our detectors we will find that they have different energy.

The reason why we find different energy to these photons than the energy that we are expecting is the result of the different relative speed between the photons and our detectors!!!

To help you understand what I'm saying I will use two examples, the one using cars and the other using protons.

First example:

Suppose we have two cars on the surface of the Earth.

The car A and the car B.

The two cars will collide with each other, and I will use two different scenarios of collision.

The car A will have a damage from the collision, and we will use this damage to determine the energy of the collision between the two cars, meaning that the car A has the role of a detector of energy on the example.

The bigger the damage on the car A, the bigger the energy of the collision!!!

First scenario: If the car A is stationary relative to the surface of the Earth and the car B is moving towards the car A at a specific speed, there will be a damage to the car A when the two cars collide.

Second scenario: While the car B is on the move, if also the car A is moving towards the car B, the damage on the car A will be bigger!!!

The car A has the role of a detector of energy on the example.

On the second scenario, the damage on the car A will be bigger (compared to the first scenario) not because the energy of the car B is higher, but because **the energy of the collision between the two cars is higher!!!**

On this example, imagine the car B as a photon and the car A as a detector!

Second example:

In particle accelerators we have various particles that collide with detectors.

Suppose that we have a proton colliding with a detector.

The detector is stationary relative to the ground and relative to us, and the proton is moving towards the detector.

The higher the speed of the proton, the higher the energy that the detector will detect on the proton.

But, **it is not the energy of the proton that is higher!!!**

Instead, **it is the energy of the collision between the proton and the detector that is higher!**

To help you understand, **imagine that a proton is stationary relative to us and a detector is moving towards the proton with high speed!!!**

When the detector will collide with the proton, again the detector will detect higher energy on the proton, but **it is the energy of the collision between the proton and the detector that will be higher, and not the energy of the proton!!!**

The detector will have a damage caused by the collision with the proton, regardless if we consider that the particle is moving towards the detector or the detector towards the particle!!!

The different damage that the detector will have is the result of the collision and not the result of the different energy of the proton!!!

Similar situations occur with photons!!!

We use various detectors in various situations, and various particles collide with them, and when I say particles I include also the photons!!!

During the collision between a particle(proton, electron, photon, etc.) and a detector, some changes will occur to the detector from the impact with the particle, and the scientific community uses these changes on the detector to determine the energy of the particle(proton, electron, photon, etc.).

But, when the scientific community thinks that the energy of a particle has changed and that's why it gives us different results on the detector during the collision, **it's not actually the energy of the particle that has changed!!!**

Instead, **it is the energy of the collision that changes due to different relative speed between the detector and the particle(proton, electron, photon, etc.)!!!**

It is a collision between two objects that are in relative motion with each other, a collision between the detector and the particle(proton, electron, photon, etc.), and **whether we consider that the particle is moving towards the detector or the detector towards the particle or both, it makes no difference!!!**

This applies to all the particles, including the photons!!!

All the protons are the same, and the reason why we find different energy during the collision between a proton and a detector is because there is different relative speed between the proton and the detector!!!

Whether we consider that the proton is moving towards the detector or the detector towards the proton it makes no difference!!!

Exactly the same applies also for the photons!!!

Specific photons that are emitted from sources through the same transition of the electrons between different energy levels, are always the same, and the reason why we find different energy during the collision between these specific photons and a detector is because there is different relative speed between the photon and the detector!!!

Whether we consider that the photon is moving towards the detector or the detector towards the photon it makes no difference!!!

Whether we consider that the particle is moving towards the detector or the detector towards the particle or both, it makes no difference because all that we have is a particle and a detector in relative motion with each other!!!

.....
More analysis and explanation about the
changes in the energy of the photons, you will find on
my paper "Gravity and the Motion of Light".
.....

The next example will help us more.

(This example is similar with the example with the **figures 4, 5-A & 5-B**, but I have added a new feature on it)

Suppose that somewhere(anywhere, it doesn't matter where) there are two light sources that are moving towards each other(**figure 6,a**).

We call these sources, **source A** and **source B**(**figure 6**).

The sources currently do not emit light.

At some point the **sources A & B** are next to each other(**figure 6**).

When the **sources A & B** are the one next to the other(**figure 6**), each source will emit two **photons**, one photon towards the direction from where the other source is coming, and the other photon towards the direction the other source is going.

So practically the two sources will emit photons towards the same two opposite directions.

But, the sources A & B will not only emit photons!!!

At the moment that the two sources are next to each other(figure 6) and emit photons, each source will also emit two protons towards the same opposite directions that will emit the two photons!!!

So, the sources A & B are sources of photons and they are also sources of protons!!!

After the emission the sources are moving away from each other because their relative motion continues.

Figure 6,a. The two sources are moving towards each other.

Figure 6. When the two sources are next to each other they will emit the photons and the protons.

So, when the two sources are next to each other (Figure 6), each source will emit simultaneously two protons and two photons!!!

The **source A** will emit the **protons E & G**, and the **source B** will emit the **protons F & H (figure 7-A)**.

Also, the **source A** emits the **photons A & C**, and the **source B** will emit the **photons B & D**. The **photons A & B** and the **protons E & F** will move towards the one direction, and the **photons C & D** with the **protons G & H** will move towards the other direction, as we see in the **figure 7-A**.

Now, suppose that the motion of the protons which are emitted by the two sources have a particularity!!!

The two protons that each source emits are not emitted with the same force by the source, and the final result will be that the protons that are emitted by the sources towards the same direction will always be next to each other!!!

So, the **protons E & F** that will be emitted towards the same direction will always be next to each other, and the **protons G & H** that will be emitted towards the other direction will also always be next to each other, as we see in the **figure 7-A!!!!**

This is similar with what will happen with the photons because the photons emitted towards the same direction will move exactly the same because their motion is not affected by the motion of their source!!!

So, there will be two groups(or pairs) of protons, the **group of the protons E & F** and the **group of the protons G & H**, as we see in the **figure 7-A!!!!**

Also, the **photons A & B** will always be next to each other and the **photons C & D** will always be next to each other, so there will also be two groups of photons, the **group of the photons A & B** and the **group of the photons C & D!!!!**

After the emission, the sources are moving away from each other because their relative motion continues!!!

Figure 7-A. Two groups of **protons** and two groups of **photons** are moving away from the two sources.

Next, there are some significant realisations regarding our assessments about the motion of the protons and the photons:

(On the **figures 7-A & 7-B** I have intentionally placed the one source exactly between the two groups of protons and the two groups of photons.)

There are two groups of **protons** moving away from the sources, and only the one of the two sources can be exactly between the two groups of **protons**, and consequently have the same distance from the two groups of **protons**(**figures 7-A, 7-B**), because the two sources are moving away from each other after the emission of the protons!!!

If the one source is exactly between the two groups of **protons**, the other source is not!!!

Exactly the same applies also for the photons!!!

There are two groups of **photons** moving away from the sources, and only the one of the two sources can be exactly between the two groups of **photons**, and consequently have the same distance from the two groups of **photons**(**figures 7-A, 7-B**), because the two sources are moving away from each other after the emission of the photons!!!

If the one source is exactly between the two groups of **photons**, the other source is not!!!

If the relative speed between the **protons E & F** and the **source A** is the same with the relative speed between the **protons G & H** and the **source A**, then the relative speed between the **protons E & F** and the **source B** is **different** than the relative speed between the **protons G & H** and the **source B**, due to the fact the source B is in relative motion with the source A!!!

Exactly the same applies also for the groups of photons!!!!!!

If the relative speed between the **photons A & B** and the **source A** is the same with the relative speed between the **photons C & D** and the **source A**, then the relative speed between the **photons A & B** and the **source B** is **different** than the relative speed between the **photons C & D** and the **source B**, due to the fact the source B is in relative motion with the source A!!!

The one group of protons is the **protons E & F** and the other group is the **protons G & H**, and only the one of the sources can be exactly between the two groups of protons, which is the **source A** on my example in the **figures 7-A & 7-B**, and that happens because the sources are in relative motion with each other!!!!

The **source B** is not exactly between the two groups of protons, and this means that the one group of protons is always closer to the **source B**, and specifically on the example in the **figure 7-B**, the **protons E & F** are always closer to the **source B** and the **protons G & H** are farther are away from the **source B**, and this is happening since the emission of the protons!!!

Exactly the same applies also for the groups of photons!!!!!!

The one group of photons is the **photons A & B** and the other group is the **photons C & D**, and only the one of the sources can be exactly between the two groups of photons, which is the **source A** on my example in the **figures 7-A & 7-B**, and that happens because the sources are in relative motion with each other!!!!

The **source B** is not exactly between the two groups of photons, and this means that the one group of photons is always closer to the **source B**, and specifically on the example in the **figure 7-B**, the **photons A & B** are always closer to the **source B** and the **photons C & D** are farther are away from the **source B**, and this is happening since the emission of the photons!!!

The distance(distance E) between the **protons E-F** and the **source A** is always the same with the distance(distance G) between the **protons G-H** and the **source A**, and this is happening since the emission of the protons, therefore, the relative speed between the **protons E-F** and the **source A** is the same(**figure 7-B**) with the relative speed between the **protons G-H** and the **source A**.

But, the distance(distance F) between the **protons E-F** and the **source B** is always **smaller** than the distance(distance H) between the **protons G-H** and the **source B**, and this is happening since the emission of the protons, therefore, the relative speed between the **protons E-F** and the **source B** is **smaller**(**figure 7-B**) than the relative speed between the **protons G-H** and the **source B**!!!!!!

Exactly the same we must say for the photons!!!!!!

The distance(distance A) between the **photons A-B** and the **source A** is always the same with the distance(distance C) between the **photons C-D** and the **source A**, and this is happening since the emission of the photons, therefore, the relative speed between the **photons A-B** and the **source A** is the same(**figure 7-B**) with the relative speed between the **photons C-D** and the **source A**.

But, the distance(distance B) between the **photons A-B** and the **source B** is always **smaller** than the distance(distance D) between the **photons C-D** and the **source B**, and this is

happening since the emission of the photons, therefore, the relative speed between the **photons A-B** and the **source B** is **smaller (figure 7-B)** than the relative speed between the **photons C-D** and the **source B!!!!!!**

Figure 7-B. The **figure 7-B** is the same with the **figure 7-A**, but additionally shows the distances. The **Distance F** is smaller than the **Distance H** & the **Distance B** is smaller than the **Distance D**.

As you can understand from the **figures 7-A & 7-B**, it makes no difference if we refer to the motion of a group of **protons** relative to a source, or if we refer to the motion of any **proton** from that group relative to the source!!!

And of course the same applies for the photons!!!

With that in mind, let's focus again on what this example shows (figure 7-B).

The **source A** emits simultaneously the **protons E & G**, and since their emission the two protons are at the same distance away from the source (**distances E & G**), which means that we will say that the relative speed between the **proton E** and the **source A** is the same with the relative speed between the **proton G** and the **source A**, meaning that there is **isotropy** of the one-way relative speeds!!!!

The **source B** emits simultaneously the **protons F & H**, and since the emission of the protons the **proton F** is **closer** to the **source B** than the **proton H** (**distance F smaller than distance H**). This means that we will say that the relative speed between the **proton F** and the **source B** is **smaller** than the relative speed between the **proton H** and the **source B**, meaning that there is **anisotropy** of the one-way relative speeds!!!!

Exactly the same applies for the photons (figure 7-B)!!!!!!!

The **source A** emits simultaneously the **photons A & C**, and since their emission the two photons are at the same distance away from the source (**distances A & C**), which means that

we will say that the relative speed between the **photon A** and the **source A** is the same with the relative speed between the **photon C** and the **source A**, meaning that there is **isotropy** of the one-way relative speeds!!!!

The **source B** emits simultaneously the **photons B & D**, and since the emission of the photons the **photon B** is **closer** to the **source B** than the **photon D**(distance **B** smaller than distance **D**). This means that we must say that the relative speed between the **photon B** and the **source B** is **smaller** than the relative speed between the **photon D** and the **source B**, meaning that there is **anisotropy** of the one-way relative speeds!!!!

On the example in the **figures 7-A & 7-B** i have intentionally placed the one source exactly between the two groups of protons and the two groups of photons, in order to show that if the one source is exactly between the groups, the other source is not!!!

The other possibility is that both sources will not be exactly between the two groups of protons and photons, and in this case there is anisotropy of the relative one-way speeds for both sources!!!

But, the possibility to have both sources exactly between the two groups of protons and photons, simply does not exist, because the sources are in relative motion with each other!!!

.....
Let's talk again about the "relativity of simultaneity" because it's extremely important!!!

We say that since their emission, the two photons and the two protons that the **source B** emits are not at the same distance from the source(**figure 7-B**), but this fact shows that there is anisotropy of the one-way speeds only if the photons and the protons are emitted simultaneously by the source!!!

The "relativity of simultaneity" has to do with events that occur at different locations!!!

When we talk about events that occur at the same location, all the humans agree about their order, and on this example(**figures 6, 7-A, 7-B**) we talk about emissions(events) on the same source, which is the **source B**!!!

There is no "relativity of simultaneity" on events that occur at the same location!!!

Let's see two examples:

If from the top of the Eiffel Tower we have emission of two protons, and according to a human on that top the two protons are emitted simultaneously, also every other human will agree with that and will say that the protons are emitted simultaneously regardless of his location and his motion!!!

If instead of that, we have an emission of one proton from the Eiffel Tower(Paris) and another emission of a proton from the Statue of Liberty(New York), and according to a human who is exactly between these two locations the emissions occur simultaneously, another human on a different location may disagree with that and according to him the emissions may not occurred simultaneously!!!

So, when we say that a source emits simultaneously two protons(or two photons), this is the reality for the source, and all the humans agree on that regardless of where they are and regardless of their motion!!!

Note that on this example(**figures 6, 7-A, 7-B**) each source emit simultaneously four particles, two photons and two protons!!!

Very significant example - Many Sources -.

On the previous examples we have only two sources of light.

But, what if we have much more light sources???

What happens if we have a thousand light sources, or a million???

In order to understand what will happen let's see an example with five light sources, because of course I cannot present an example with a million sources!!!

Suppose that somewhere there are five sources of light, and each source is in relative motion with each of the other sources(**figure 8,a**), at different relative speed with each source.

The thing that is common in all the relative motions between the sources is that the sources are moving towards each other(**figure 8,a**).

All the sources currently do not emit light.

These light sources are having various relative speeds between them, and to make the example simpler, let's say that they are moving only towards two directions that are opposite to each other(**figure 8,a**).

At some point, as the five sources were moving towards each other, we end up in a situation where the light sources are the one next to the other, as we see in the **figure 8**.

When the five light sources are the one next to the other(**figure 8**), they will all emit two photons towards the two opposite directions towards which the sources are moving(one photon towards each direction).

After the emission of the photons, the sources are moving away from each other because their relative motions continues.

Figure 8,a. The light sources are moving towards each other.

Figure 8. When the light sources are next to each other they will emit the photons.

The photons which are emitted by the five light sources, will create two groups of photons which are moving towards two opposite directions, like we see in the **figure 9**.

Question: How many of the five sources can be located exactly between the two groups of photons???

Answer: Only one of them, or none of them!!!!

So, there are five sources of light, and only one of them can be located exactly between the two groups of photons, meaning that this source will have the same distance from the two groups of photons(**figure 9**), which means that there can be isotropy of the one-way speed of light for only the one of the five light sources!!!

For the other four light sources there is anisotropy of the one-way speed of light, because for each of the other four light sources the reality is that the two groups of photons are not at the same distance away from the sources(**figure 9**), and this means that the two photons that a source has emit are always not at the same distance away from the source, and **this is happening since the emission of the photons!!!**

The other possibility is that all five light sources will not be located exactly between the two groups of photons, which means that there will be anisotropy of the one-way speed of light for all five light sources, but the possibility to have all the light sources located exactly between the two groups of photons does not exist because the sources are in relative motion with each other!!!

Only one of the light sources can be located exactly between the two groups of photons, or none of the sources!!!

Figure 9. Only one of the five sources may be exactly between the two groups of photons, meaning that only for the one of the five sources there is isotropy of the one-way speed of light! For the other four light sources there is anisotropy of the one-way speed of light!

And the most important realisation:

If there were a million light sources, instead of five, in relative motion with each other, only one of the million sources could have been exactly between the two groups of photons, meaning that we could have isotropy of the speed of light only for the one of the million sources, which means that **the anisotropy of the one-way speed of light is what usually occurs!!!**

The anisotropy of the one-way speed of light relative to a source is not the result of different motion of the photons!!!

The photons emitted by any source will make the same motion!!!!

The fact that there is anisotropy of the one-way speed of light relative to a source does not contradict to the fact that the motion of light is independent from the motion of the source!!!

In fact, this is actually the reason why there is anisotropy, meaning that **the reason why there is anisotropy of the one-way speed of light relative to its source, is the fact that all the photons are making the same motion regardless of the motion of their source!!!!**

And the question is: Relative to what, the photons are making the same motion regardless of the motion of their source, because as we see in the **figure 9**, all the photons that are moving towards the same direction are making the same motion and are stationary relative to each other???

Until now we have seen examples with sources emitting only two photons towards opposite directions.

Next we will see an example with sources emitting **light waves towards all directions!**

Suppose that somewhere (anywhere, it doesn't matter where) there are three light sources, and each source is in relative motion with each of the other two sources (**figure 10,a**) and at different relative speed with each source.

The thing that is common in all relative motions between the three sources is that the sources are moving closer to each other.

In their motion relative to each other, the three sources are moving only towards two directions that are opposite to each other.

All the sources currently do not emit light.

At some point the three sources are the one next to the other, as we see in the **figure 10**.

When the three sources are the one next to the other (**figure 10**), each source will emit a wave of light towards all directions.

After the emission of light, the sources are moving away from each other because they continue to be in relative motion with each other.

Figure 10,a . Three light sources are moving towards each other.

Figure 10. When the three sources of light are next to each other, they will emit a wave of light towards all directions.

Three expanding light waves will be created, one from each of the three sources, as the **figure 11 shows**.

The three light waves will expand with exactly the same way, as we see in the **figure 11**, and basically we can say that the three waves will be stationary relative to each other.

But, because of the fact that the three light sources are moving away from each other after the emission of the light, there cannot be all three sources at the hypothetical centre of the light wave that they have emit!!!!!!

The one possibility is that only the one of the three sources will be at the hypothetical centre of the light wave that is has emit(see **figure 11**), and the other possibility is that all three sources will not be at the centre of the light wave that they have emit, but the possibility to have all three sources at the centre of the light wave that they have emit, simply does not exist!!!!!!

This means that at least the two of the sources will not be at the centre of the light wave that they have emit(**figure 11**), and of course this mean that there will be anisotropy of the one-way speed of light for at least the two of the sources!!!

On the example in the **figure 11** i have intentionally placed the **red light source** at the hypothetical centre of its own light wave, in order to show that if the one source is at the centre of its own light wave, the other sources are not!!!!

The only other possibility is that all the sources will not be at the centre of their own light wave!!!

As we see on the **figure 11**, the green light source is more off-centre relative to its own wave than the blue light source, meaning that the one-way anisotropy is larger for the green light source.

But, the anisotropy is not the result of different motion of the photons!!!

The photons emitted by the three sources are moving exactly the same, but due to that fact, meaning due to the fact that the photons moving in exactly the same way, and due to the fact that the sources are in relative motion with each other, there cannot be all the sources at the centre of the light wave that they have emit!!!

Figure 11. Presents a situation where the one of the sources is at the hypothetical centre of the light wave that it has emit. On this figure, the red light source is at the centre of its own light wave. There cannot be all the light sources at the centre of their own light wave.

Where we can see a manifestation of the anisotropy of the one-way speed of photons relative to their source???

We can see it on the "Sagnac effect" on the original experiment from Georges Sagnac, on the "Sagnac effect" on the GPS systems, and on the Michelson-Gale-Pearson experiment.

Next I will present examples using the "Sagnac effect" in order to see the anisotropy, see what actually happens on the "Sagnac effect", and see exactly the same phenomenon that we see in the previous examples(see **figures 5,7,9**) where I have used linear motion and emission of photons and protons.

On the examples so far(**figures 5,7,9**) where I have used linear motion, we have two groups of photons, and sources that are in relative motion with each other, and we understand that only the one of the sources can have the same distance from the two groups of photons, meaning that for the other sources that do not have the same distance from the two groups of photons there is anisotropy of the one-way speed of light!!!

On the example that I will present next, which is based on the Sagnac experiment, and I will use rotational/revolutionary/circular motion, we will also have two groups of photons, and sources which are in relative motion with each other(like in the linear motion), and we will see that only the one of the sources can have the same distance from the two groups of photons, meaning that for the other sources that do not have the same distance from the two groups of photons there is anisotropy of the one-way speed of light!!!

So, on the following examples I will use rotational/revolutionary/circular motion(because I want to show the Sagnac effect), and we will see that there is no difference in our conclusions between linear motion(**figures 5, 7, 9**) and rotational/revolutionary/circular motion.

Before we focus on the "Sagnac effect" while using photons, I will present an example using balls, where we will see the same phenomenon that we will see later where we will use photons!!!

The example with the balls will be very helpful in our attempt see the occurrence of the anisotropy.

We will see that it doesn't matter if we use balls, protons or photons!!!

The results are the same!

On the next example I will use balls in order to see that there is no difference if we use balls or photons, like on the **figure 7-B** example I have used protons in order to see that there is no difference regardless if we use protons or photons!!!

Let's start with the example with the balls.

Suppose that we have in our possession seven flat surfaces made of steel.

We also have a device that ejects small balls made of elastic material at very high speed, and it ejects the balls towards two opposite directions.

The device that ejects the small elastic balls we call it "**source**", because is the source of the balls.

The device can eject the balls towards the flat surfaces and the balls will bounce/reflect to the them, and so the seven flat surfaces we call them "**reflectors**".

We place the **reflectors** and the **source** in the surface of the Earth, and we place them in such a way that they form a circle, as we see in the **figure 12**.

At some point the **source** ejects simultaneously two balls, one ball with a direction towards the reflector on the right, which we have called **reflector 1**, and the other ball towards the reflector on the left, which we have called **reflector 7** (**figure 13**).

The ball ejected towards the right is the **ball 1**, and the ball ejected towards the left is the **ball 2**.

The balls are ejected with very high speed, and due to the fact they are bouncy and durable, after they bounce/reflect to the first reflector they have the momentum to reflect to all the other reflectors, and they will complete a circle returning to their source from the other side (figure 14).

The **ball 1** will first bounce/reflect to the **reflector 1**, and then will reflect to the **reflector 2**, and after that will reflect to the **reflector 3**, and so on, as we see in the **figure 13**, and will return to the source from the left side after it will reflect to the **reflector 7**, as we see in the **figure 14**.

The **ball 2** will first bounce/reflect to the **reflector 7**, and then will reflect to the **reflector 6**, and after that will reflect to the **reflector 5**, and so on, as we see in the **figure 13**, and will return to the source from the right side after it will reflect to the **reflector 1**, as we see in the **figure 14**.

Figure 13. As the balls 1 & 2 are moving away from the source they always are at the same distance away from it, and this means that the two balls were having the same speed relative to the source.

The **balls 1 & 2**(**figures 13-14**) are having the same speed relative to the **source**.

But what do we mean when we say that the **balls 1 & 2** are having the same speed relative to the **source**???

We mean that as the two balls are moving away from the source, they always are at the same distance away from the source, since the **source** ejects the two **balls** simultaneously!!!

If the **balls 1 & 2** are not having the same distance from the **source** as they are moving away from it, and since they are ejected simultaneously by the source, in that case we will say that the two balls are not having the same speed relative to the source!!!

But, if the **balls 1 & 2** are at the same distance away from the source as they are moving away from it, of course we will say that the **balls 1 & 2** are having the same speed relative to the source!!!

Due to the fact that the **balls 1 & 2** are having the same speed relative to the **source** and will always be at the same distance from the source, they will return back to the source simultaneously, as we see in the **figure 14**!!!!

In fact, the fact that the **balls 1 & 2** return to the **source** simultaneously is the result of the fact that they have the same speed relative to the source, since the source has ejected the balls simultaneously and since the balls are moving on the same path/course!!!

If the **balls 1 & 2** will not return to the **source** simultaneously, we will say that the balls are not having the same speed relative to the source, since they are ejected simultaneously by the source and since they are moving on the same path/course.

If the **balls 1 & 2** will not return to the **source** simultaneously, we will say that the balls are not having the same speed relative to the source, even without knowing anything else about the motion of the balls!!!

For example, let's say that we don't watch the **balls 1 & 2** as they are moving away from the **source**, and the only thing that we know is the fact that the balls will return simultaneously to the source!!!

The fact that the balls will return to the source simultaneously is something that will make us understand that the speed of the **balls 1 & 2** relative to the **source** is the same, since the balls are ejected simultaneously by the source and since the balls are moving on the same path/course!!!

If the **balls 1 & 2** will not return simultaneously to the source, we will say that the speeds of the two balls relative to the source are different, since they are ejected simultaneously by the source and since they are moving on the same path/course.

The **ball 1** will return to the source from the left side after it will reflect to all the reflectors, and the **ball 2** will return to the source from the right side after it will reflect to all the reflectors, as we see in the **figure 14**.

The two balls will return simultaneously to the source, as the **figure 14** shows.

Figure 14. Balls 1 & 2 completing a circle.

Next, let's make the previous example a little bit more complicated.

We have again the same **seven reflectors** and the same **source** placed on the surface of the Earth, arranged as before to form a circle.

But this time we will add two more sources on our example/experiment.

The **source** which is stationary on the surface of the Earth and forms the circle together with the seven reflectors, now we call it **red source**(**figure 15**).

On this version of the example/experiment there are two more sources/ejectors of balls which are on the move relative to the red source.

The one source is the **green source** and the other is the **blue source**(**figures 15-16-17-18**).

The **green** and the **blue source** are placed in two different platforms which are rotating on the inside of the circle that the seven reflectors are forming.

We have put one source on each platform.

The two platforms are placed at different heights.

The two platforms are identical and the two sources are placed on the same location on each platform, and so when the platforms rotate the two sources make identical circular motions, and they pass at the same distance from the reflectors as they are moving next to them.

The two platforms rotate towards opposite directions meaning that also the **blue** and the **green source** are rotating towards opposite directions.

The two platforms rotate at the same speed, and so the **green** and the **blue source** are having the same speed relative to the **red source**, but if we want we can create a different example with the **green & blue source** not to have the same speed relative to the **red source**.

At some point, as the platforms rotate, the **green & blue source** are both next to the **red source**(**figure 15**).

(The **figure 15** is not completely accurate and I will explain why.

As the two platforms rotate and the **blue & green source** are moving next to the reflectors they will actually have the same distance from the reflectors, and of course when they pass in front of the red source the two sources will also have the same distance from it because they will be at different height because the platforms are at different height.

That happens because the two platforms are identical and the two sources are placed on the same location on the platforms.

But, on the **figure 15** i have drawn the three sources the one next to the other side by side, with the green source to be closer towards the centre of the circle that it is created by the seven reflectors, because there was no other way to show that the three sources were next to each other.

I did that because the **figure 15** shows how the situation looks like from above looking down, and in order to show that the **blue** and the **green source** are both next to the **red source**, there was no other way but to draw them side by side.

In reality what will happen is that both the **green** and the **blue source** are exactly next to the **red source**, but the one source is at a lower height and the other source is above it because the two platforms are at different heights.

So actually, the one source is slightly below the **red source** and the other source is slightly above the **red source**.

In the rest of the pictures the **green & blue source** are at the same distance from the reflectors.)

When the **red, green & blue sources** are next to each other(**figure 15**), all three sources will eject two balls, one towards the reflector 1 and the other towards the reflector 7.

Figure 15. When the three sources are next to each other they will eject the balls.

The **red source** ejects the **ball A** towards the reflector 1 and the **ball D** towards the reflector 7(**figure 16**).

The **blue source** ejects the **ball B** towards the reflector 1 and the **ball E** towards the reflector 7(**figure 16**).

The **green source** ejects the **ball C** towards the reflector 1 and the **ball F** towards the reflector 7(**figure 16**).

Each source ejects the two balls simultaneously.

The **balls A & D** that the **red source** ejects are making the same motion that the **balls 1 & 2** were making in the previous example in the **figures 13-14**, meaning that the **balls A & D** are having the same speed relative to the **red source**, which means that as the **balls A & D** are moving away from the **red source** are always at the same distance from it.

And next we go to the important part of the example/experiment.

The two balls that each of the other two sources (blue & green) will eject, are not ejected with the same force by the source, meaning that the **blue source** does not eject the **balls B & E** with the same force and the **green source** does not eject the **balls C & F** with the same force!!!

The result is the following:

The **balls B & C** that are ejected by the **blue & green source** towards the same direction with the **ball A**, are forming a group with the **ball A** meaning that the **balls A, B & C** are always next to each other (**figures 16-17-18**)!!!!

The **balls E & F** that are ejected by the **blue & green source** towards the same direction with the **ball D**, are forming a group with the **ball D** meaning that the **balls D, E & F** are always next to each other (**figures 16-17-18**)!!!!

So we have a situation where the **balls A, B & C** are moving exactly the same regardless of the motion of their source, and also the **balls D, E & F** are moving exactly the same regardless of the motion of their source, meaning that we have a motion of the balls that is similar to the motion of the photons, where we have seen that the motion of the photons is always the same regardless of the motion of the source!!!!

The **balls A-B-C** will be always next to each other and will reflect to each reflector simultaneously while being next to each other, and also the **balls D-E-F** will be always next to each other and will reflect to each reflector simultaneously while being next to each other (**figures 16-17-18**).

The balls of each group are not at the same height from the ground due to the fact that their sources are not at the same height from the ground, and so they will hit to every reflector simultaneously as they are moving as a group and being always next to each other (**figures 16-17-18**).

(On the **figures 16-17-18** i have drawn the balls of each group the one next to the other side by side because there was no other way to show that the three balls were next to each other.

In reality what will happen is that while the three balls of each group will be next to each other and will be hitting simultaneously to the reflectors, they will be at a different height from the ground.

But because the **figures 16-17-18** are showing how the situation looks like from above looking down, in order to show that the three balls of each group are next to each other and are simultaneously next to a reflector, there was no other way but to draw them side by side.

Because if you are watching the situation from above looking down and the balls are hitting simultaneously the reflectors but being at a different height, you will see only one ball, the ball that it is closer to you.

So, in order for the figures to showing all the balls there was no other way but to draw them side by side.)

Figure 16. Two groups of balls are moving away from the sources.

So, as we see in the **figure 16**, what happens is that there are two groups of balls (**group A-B-C & group D-E-F**) moving away from the three sources(**red, blue & green source**), while bouncing to the reflectors.

The two groups of balls will reflect to all the reflectors one after the other and complete a circle, like the **balls 1 & 2** did in the previous example(**figures 12-13-14**).

While the **two groups of balls** moving away from the **three sources**, the three sources were moving away from each other and will no longer be next to each other(**figure 16**)!!!

The three sources were next to each other when they ejected the balls(**figure 15**), but afterwards they are moving away from each other(**figure 16**)!!!

The **balls A & D** which are ejected by the **red source** are having the same speed relative to their source, meaning that they are always at the same distance away from the red source, and the **balls B & C** are always at the same location with the **ball A** and also the **balls E & F** are always at the same location with the **ball D**(**figure 17-A**).

Therefore, instead of talking about the motion of the **ball A** relative to the **red source**, we can talk about the motion of the group of the **balls A-B-C** relative to the **red source**, and instead of talking about the motion of the **ball D** relative to the **red source**, we can talk about the motion of the group of the **balls D-E-F** relative to the **red source**!!!!!!

So, the relative speed between the group of the **balls A-B-C** and the **red source** is the same with the relative speed between the group of the **balls D-E-F** and the **red source**, and by that we mean that as the two groups of balls are moving away from the red source, they are always at the same distance away from the red source!!!

As we see on the **figure 17-A** the distance A is the same with the distance B!!!!

But, which is the speed of the two groups of balls relative to the blue and the green source???

Figure 17-A. Distance A equal to Distance B.

The **green source** is on the move relative to the **red source**, therefore, if the two groups of balls are at the same distance from the **red source** they are not at the same distance away from the **green source**!!!

As the **figure 17-B** shows, the distance A which is the distance between the group of the **balls A-B-C** and the **green source** is **smaller** than the distance B which is the distance between the

balls D-E-F and the **green source**, meaning that as the two groups of balls are moving away from the green source, the group of the **balls A-B-C** is always at a closer distance to the **green source** than the group of the **balls D-E-F!!!!**

Figure 17-B. Distance A smaller than Distance B.

The **green source** has ejected the **balls C & F**, but it makes no difference if we refer to the motion of the **balls C & F** relative to the **green source** or if we refer to the motion of the two groups of balls(**group A-B-C & group D-E-F**) relative to the **green source!!!**

It's the same thing because since the ejection of the six balls by the three sources, the **balls A, B & C** are always at the same location and the **balls D, E & F** are also always at the same location!!!

Since the ejection of the six balls by the three sources and the creation of the two groups of balls, the group of the **balls A-B-C** is closer to the **green source** than the group of the **balls D-E-F**(**figure 17-B**)!!!

Therefore, we will say that the speed of the **balls A-B-C** relative to the **green source** is smaller than the speed of the **balls D-E-F** relative to the **green source**!!!!

We cannot say anything different than that!!!!

If we say that the speed of the **balls A-B-C** relative to the **red source** is the same with the speed of the **balls D-E-F** relative to the **red source**(**figure 17-A**), then we must say that the speed of the **balls A-B-C** relative to the **green source** is smaller than the speed of the **balls D-E-F** relative to the **green source**(**figure 17-B**)!!!!

The **blue source** is on the move relative to the **red source**, therefore, if the two groups of balls are at the same distance from the **red source** they are not at the same distance away from the **blue source**!!!

As the **figure 17-C** shows, the distance A which is the distance between the group of the **balls A-B-C** and the **blue source** is larger than the distance B which is the distance between the **balls D-E-F** and the **blue source**, meaning that as the two groups of balls are moving away from the blue source, the group of the **balls A-B-C** is always at a larger distance away from the **blue source** than the group of the **balls D-E-F**!!!

The **blue source** has ejected the **balls B & E**, but it makes no difference if we refer to the motion of the **balls B & E** relative to the **blue source** or if we refer to the motion of the two groups of balls(**group A-B-C & group D-E-F**) relative to the **blue source**!!!

It's the same thing because since the ejection of the six balls by the three sources, the **balls A, B & C** are always at the same location and the **balls D, E & F** are also always at the same location!!!

Since the ejection of the six balls by the three sources and the creation of the two groups of balls, the group of the **balls A-B-C** is farther away from the **blue source** than the group of the **balls D-E-F**(**figure 17-C**)!!!

Therefore, we will say that the speed of the **balls A-B-C** relative to the **blue source** is larger than the speed of the **balls D-E-F** relative to the **blue source**!!!!

We cannot say anything different than that!!!!

If we say that the speed of the **balls A-B-C** relative to the **red source** is the same with the speed of the **balls D-E-F** relative to the **red source**(**figure 17-A**), then we must say that the speed of the **balls A-B-C** relative to the **blue source** is larger than the speed of the **balls D-E-F** relative to the **blue source**(**figure 17-C**)!!!

Figure 17-C. Distance A larger than Distance B.

Now let's summarise our conclusions about this example/experiment:

The relative speed between the **balls A, B & C** and the **red source** is the same with the relative speed between the **balls D, E & F** and the **red source**, because since the ejection of the six balls and the creation of the two moving groups of balls, the distance between the **balls A, B & C** and the **red source** is the same with the distance between the **balls D, E & F** and the **red source**(figure 17-A).

The relative speed between the **balls A, B & C** and the **green source** is smaller than the relative speed between the **balls D, E & F** and the **green source**, because since the ejection of the six balls and the creation of the two moving groups of balls, the distance between the **balls A, B & C** and the **green source** is smaller than the distance between the **balls D, E & F** and the **green source**(figure 17-B).

The relative speed between the **balls A, B & C** and the **blue source** is larger than the relative speed between the **balls D, E & F** and the **blue source**, because since the ejection of the six balls and the creation of the two moving groups of balls, the distance between the **balls A, B & C** and the **blue source** is larger than the distance between the **balls D, E & F** and the **blue source**(figure 17-C).

As the motion of the balls continues and they keep reflecting to the reflectors, what will happen is that the **balls A-B-C** will meet the **blue source** before the **balls D-E-F**, and the **balls D-E-F** will meet the **green source** before the **balls A-B-C**, as we see in the **figure 18!!!**

The two group of balls will meet the **red source** simultaneously!!!

The **balls A-B-C** will meet the **blue source** before completing one circle(**figure 18**), but in order to meet the **green source** they will complete more than one circle!!!

The **balls D-E-F** will meet the **green source** before completing one circle(**figure18**), but in order to meet the **blue source** they will complete more than one circle!!!

Figure 18. The two group of balls(A,B,C & D,E,F) are close to completing a circle.

Of course you have seen that what I present on this example is similar with the examples in the **figures 7-B & 9**, where I have used linear motion and emission of photons and protons.

On the examples in the **figures 7-B & 9**, we have two groups of photons or two groups of protons that are moving away from their sources, and sources that are moving away from each other, and here on the example with the **figures 17-A, 17-B & 17-C** we have two groups of balls that are moving away from their sources/ejectors, and sources/ejectors that are moving away from each other!!!

As you see there is no difference in our assessments and conclusions between linear motion(figures 7-B & 9**) and rotational/revolutionary//circular motion(**figures 17-A, 17-B, 17-C**), and there is no difference in our assessments and conclusions regardless if we have motion of photons, protons or balls!!!**

Next let's see what will happen if instead of ejecting balls the **sources will emit photons!!!**

Will there be any differences???

Our conclusions will be different when we use photons instead of balls???

Let's start our example/experiment.

Suppose that we have in our possession **seven mirrors** and one **source of light**.

We place the **mirrors** and the **light source** in the surface of the Earth, and we place them in such a way that they form a circle, as we see in the **figure 19**.

At some point the light source emits simultaneously two photons, one photon with a direction towards the mirror on the right, which we have called **mirror 1**, and the other photon towards the mirror on the left, which we have called **mirror 7**(**figure 20**).

The photon emitted towards the right is the **photon 1**, and the photons emitted towards the left is the **photon 2**.

Each photon, after it will reflect to the first mirror, will reflect to the all the other mirrors, completing a circle and returning to the source from the other side.

The **photon 1** will first reflect to the **mirror 1**, and then will reflect to the **mirror 2**, and after that will reflect to the **mirror 3**, and so on, as we see in the **figure 20**, and will return to the source from the left side after it will reflect to the **mirror 7**.

The **photon 2** will first reflect to the **mirror 7**, and then will reflect to the **mirror 6**, and after that will reflect to the **mirror 5**, and so on, as we see in the **figure 20**, and will return to the source from the right side after it will reflect to the **mirror 1**.

Figure 20. As the photons 1 & 2 are moving away from the source they always are at the same distance away from it, and this means that the two photons were having the same speed relative to the source.

The **photons 1 & 2**(**figures 20-21**) are having the same speed relative to the **light source**. But what do we mean when we say that the **photons 1 & 2** are having the same speed relative to the **source**???

We mean that as the two photons are moving away from the source, they always are at the same distance away from the source, since the **source** emits the two **photons** simultaneously! If the **photons 1 & 2** were not having the same distance from the **source** as they are moving away from it, and since they are emitted simultaneously by the source, in that case we must say that the two photons are not having the same speed relative to the source!!!

But, the **photons 1 & 2** actually will be at the same distance away from the source as they are moving away from it, and of course we must say that the **photons 1 & 2** are having the same speed relative to the source!!!

Due to the fact the **photons 1 & 2** are having the same speed relative to the **light source** and will always be at the same distance from the source, they will back to the source simultaneously, as we see in the **figure 21**!!!

In fact, the fact that the **photons 1 & 2** return to the **light source** simultaneously is the result of the fact that they have the same speed relative to the source, since the source has emitted the two photons simultaneously and since they are moving on the same path/course!!!

If the **photons 1 & 2** will not return to the **source** simultaneously, we will say that the photons are not having the same speed relative to the source, since they are emitted simultaneously by the source and since they are moving on the same path/course!!!!

The **photon 1** will return to the **light source** from the left side after it will reflect to all the mirrors, and the **photon 2** will return to the **light source** from the right side after it will reflect to all the mirrors, as we see in the **figure 21**.

The two photons will return simultaneously to the source, as the **figure 21** shows.

Figure 21. The photons 1 & 2 completing a circle.

Next let's make the previous example a little bit more complicated, as we did when we were using balls.

We have again the same **seven mirrors** and the same **light source** placed on the surface of the Earth, arranged as before to form a circle.

But this time we will add two more light sources on our example/experiment.

The **source** which is stationary on the surface of the Earth and forms the circle together with the seven mirrors, now we call it **red light source**(**figure 22**).

On this version of the example/experiment there are two more light sources which are on the move relative to the red light source.

The one source is the **green light source** and the other is the **blue light source**(**figures 22-23-24-25**).

The **green** and the **blue light source** are placed in two different platforms, one source on each platform, which are rotating on the inside of the circle that the seven mirrors are forming.

The two platforms are placed at different heights.

The two platforms are identical and the two sources are placed on the same location on each platform, and so when the platforms rotate the two sources make identical circular motions, and they pass at the same distance from the mirrors as they are moving next to them.

The two platforms rotate towards opposite directions meaning that also the **blue** and the **green light source** are rotating towards opposite directions.

The two platforms rotate at the same speed, and so relative to the **red light source** the **green** and the **blue light source** are having the same speed, but if we want we can create an example with the **green & blue sources** not to have the same speed relative to the **red source**.

At some point the **green** and the **blue light source** are both next to the **red light source**(**figure 22**).

(As I did previously on the **figure 15**, on the **figure 22** i have drawn the three light sources the one next to the other side by side for the same reasons.

This means that we see the green light source next to the blue source but what actually happens is that both sources are next to the red source, but the one is at a lower height and the other is above it because the two platforms are at different heights, but because the **figure 22** shows how the situation looks like from above looking down, in order to show that the **blue** and the **green light source** are both next to the **red source**, there was no other way but to draw them side by side.

In the rest of the pictures the **green** and the **blue light source** are at the same distance from the mirrors.)

When the **red, green & blue sources** are next to each other(**figure 22**), all three sources will emit two photons, one towards the mirror 1 and the other towards the mirror 7.

Figure 22. When the three sources are next to each other they will emit the photons.

The **red light source** emits the **photon A** towards the mirror 1 and the **photon D** towards the mirror 7 (**figure 23**).

The **blue light source** emits the **photon B** towards the mirror 1 and the **photon E** towards the mirror 7 (**figure 23**).

The **green light source** emits the **photon C** towards the mirror 1 and the **photon F** towards the mirror 7 (**figure 23**).

Each source emits the two photons simultaneously.

What will happen after the emission of the photons is that there will be created two groups of photons(**figure 23**).

The **photons A & D** will make the same motion that the **photons 1 & 2** were making in the previous example(**figures 19-20-21**).

The **photons B & C** will make identical motion with the **photon A**, and the **photons E & F** will make identical motion with the **photon D**(**figure 23**).

The **photons A, B, & C** will move exactly the same regardless of the motion of their source, and will move as a group practically being always next to each other(**figures 23-24-25**).

The same applies for the **photons D, E & F** that are emitted towards the other direction.

The **photons A-B-C** will be always next to each other and will reflect to each mirror simultaneously while being next to each other, and also the **photons D-E-F** will be always next to each other and will reflect to each mirror while being next to each other(**figures 23-24-25**).

The photons of each group are not at the same height from the ground due to the fact that their sources are not at the same height from the ground, and so they will hit to every mirror simultaneously as they are moving as a group and being always next to each other(**figures 23-24-25**).

(On the **figures 23-24-25** i have drawn the photons of each group the one next to the other side by side because there was no other way to show that the three photons were next to each other.

In reality what will happen is that the three photons of each group will be next to each other and will hit simultaneously the mirrors but they are at a different height from the ground.

But because the **figures 23-24-25** are showing how the situation looks like from above looking down, in order to show that the three photons of each group are next to each other and are simultaneously next to a mirror, there was no other way but to draw them side by side.

Because, if you are watching the situation from above looking down and the photons are hitting simultaneously the mirrors but being at a different height, you will see only one photon, the photon that it is closer to you.

So, in order for the pictures to showing all the photons there was no other way but to draw them side by side.)

Figure 23. Two groups of photons are moving away from the sources.

So, as we see in the **figure 23**, what happens is that there are two groups of photons (**group A-B-C & group D-E-F**) moving away from the three sources (**red, blue & green light source**), while reflecting to the mirrors.

The two groups of photons will reflect to all the mirrors one after the other and complete a circle, like the photons 1 & 2 did in the previous example (figures 19-20-21).

While the two groups of photons moving away from the three light sources, the three light sources are moving away from each other and will no longer be next to each other (figure 23)! The three light sources were next to each other when they emitted the photons (figure 22), but afterwards they are moving away from each other (figure 23)!!!

Since the emission of the six photons there are two groups of photons moving away from the three sources.

The **red light source** emits the **photons A & D**, and the **photons B & C** are always at the same location with the **photon A**, and the **photons E & F** are always at the same location with the **photon D (figure 24-A)**.

Therefore, instead of talking about the motion of the **photon A** relative to the **red light source**, we can talk about the motion of the group of the **photons A-B-C** relative to the **red light source**, and instead of talking about the motion of the **photon D** relative to the **red light source**, we can talk about the motion of the group of the **photons D-E-F** relative to the **red light source!!!**

As the two groups of photons are moving away from the **red light source** they are always at the same distance from the red light source (distance A equal to distance B, **figure 24-A**) and eventually the two groups of photons will return to the **red light source** simultaneously after completing one circle, as we see in the **figure 25**.

This means that the relative speed between the group of the **photons A-B-C** and the **red light source** is the same with the relative speed between the group of the **photons D-E-F** and the **red light source**.

But, which is the speed of the two groups of photons relative to the blue and the green light source???

Figure 24-A. Distance A equal to Distance B.

The **green light source** is on the move relative to the **red light source**, therefore, if the two groups of photons(**group A,B,C & group D,E,F**) are at the same distance away from the **red source**, they are not at the same distance away from the **green source**, because after the emission of the photons the **green light source** is moving away from the **red light source!!!** As the **figure 24-B** shows, the distance A which is the distance between the group of the **photons A-B-C** and the **green light source** is smaller than the distance B which is the distance between the **photons D-E-F** and the **green light source**, meaning that after the emission of the six photons, as the two groups of photons are moving away from the green light source, the group of the **photons A-B-C** is always at a closer distance to the **green light source** than the group of the **photons D-E-F!!!!**

This is something that is happening since the emission of the six photons!!!

Since the emission of the six photons and the creation of the two groups of photons(photons A,B,C & photons D,E,F),the one group is always closer to the green light source(**figure 24-B**). This is anisotropy of the speed of light relative to the green light source!!!

And of course this is exactly the same with what is happening on the example in the **figure 17-B**, where we have balls instead of photons!!!

Therefore, what applies in the one case also applies in the other, and whatever we say in the one case(balls) we must say in the other(photons)!!!

The same assessments and conclusions that we have on the example with the balls we must also have on the example with the photons because they are identical!!!

The **green light source** has emit the **photons C & F**, but it makes no difference if we refer to the motion of the **photons C & F** relative to the **green light source** or if we refer to the motion of the two groups of photons(**group A,B,C & group D,E,F**) relative to the **green light source!** It's the same thing because since the emission of the six photons by the three sources, the **photons A, B & C** are always at the same location and the **photons D, E & F** are also always at the same location!!!

Since the emission of the six photons by the three sources and the creation of the two groups of photons, the group of the **photons A-B-C** is closer to the **green light source** than the group of the **photons D-E-F(figure 24-B)!!!**

It's exactly the same with what we see in the **figure 17-B**, in the example where we have used balls instead of photons!!!

Therefore, we will say that the speed of the **photons A-B-C** relative to the **green light source** is smaller than the speed of the **photons D-E-F** relative to the **green source!!!**

We cannot say anything different than that!!!!

If we say that the speed of the **photons A-B-C** relative to the **red light source** is the same with the speed of the **photons D-E-F** relative to the **red light source(figure 24-A)**, then we must say that the speed of the **photons A-B-C** relative to the **green light source** is smaller than the speed of the **photons D-E-F** relative to the **green light source(figure 24-B)!!!!**

What we see here where we have **rotational/revolutionary/circular motion** is exactly the same with what is happening in **linear motion** which we see in the examples in the **figures 5-B, 7-B & 9.**

Figure 24-B. Distance A smaller than Distance B.

The **blue light source** is on the move relative to the **red light source**, therefore, if the two groups of photons(**group A,B,C** & **group D,E,F**) are at the same distance away from the **red light source**, they are not at the same distance away from the **blue light source**, because after the emission of the photons the **blue light source** is moving away from the **red light source**!!! As the **figure 24-C** shows, the distance A which is the distance between the group of the **photons A-B-C** and the **blue light source** is larger than the distance B which is the distance between the **photons D-E-F** and the **blue light source**, meaning that after the emission of the six photons, as the two groups of photons are moving away from the blue light source, the group of the **photons A-B-C** is always at a larger distance away from the **blue light source** than the group of the **photons D-E-F**!!!

This is something that is happening since the emission of the six photons!!! Since the emission of the six photons and the creation of the two groups of photons(photons A,B,C & photons D,E,F), the one group is always closer to the blue light source(**figure 24-C**). This is anisotropy of the speed of light relative to the blue light source!!!

And of course this is exactly the same with what is happening in the example in the **figure 17-C**, where we have balls instead of photons!!!!

Therefore, what applies in the one case also applies in the other, and whatever we say in the one case(balls) we must say in the other(photons)!!!

The same assessments and conclusions that we have on the example with the balls we must also have on the example with the photons because they are identical!!!

The **blue light source** has emit the **photons B & E**, but it makes no difference if we refer to the motion of the **photons B & E** relative to the **blue light source** or if we refer to the motion of the two groups of photons(**group A,B,C & group D,E,F**) relative to the **blue light source**! It's the same thing because since the emission of the six photons by the three light sources, the **photons A, B & C** are always at the same location and the **photons D, E & F** are also always at the same location!!!

Since the emission of the six photons by the three sources and the creation of the two groups of photons, the group of the **photons A-B-C** is farther away from the **blue light source** than the group of the **photons D-E-F**(**figure 24-C**)!!!!

It's exactly the same with what we see in the **figure 17-C**, in the example where we have used balls instead of photons!!!

Therefore, we will say that the speed of the **photons A-B-C** relative to the **blue light source** is larger than the speed of the **photons D-E-F** relative to the **blue light source**!!!!

We cannot say anything different than that!!!!

If we say that the speed of the **photons A-B-C** relative to the **red light source** is the same with the speed of the **photons D-E-F** relative to the **red light source**(**figure 24-A**), then we must say that the speed of the **photons A-B-C** relative to the **blue light source** is larger than the speed of the **photons D-E-F** relative to the **blue light source**(**figure 24-C**)!!!!

What we see here where we have **rotational/revolutionary/circular motion** is exactly the same with what is happening in **linear motion**, like we see in the examples in the **figures 5-B, 7-B & 9**.

Here(**figures 23, 24-A, 24-B, 24-C**) we have three light sources in relative motion with each other and two groups of photons emitted by the sources, but only the one source has the same distance from the two groups of photons, meaning that for the other two sources there is anisotropy of the one-way speed of light!!!!

This is similar with what we have seen in the previous examples(**figures 5-B, 7-B & 9**) where i have used linear motion and emission of photons and protons!!!

Figure 24-C. Distance A larger than Distance B.

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An extremely important note:

On the original experiment by Georges Sagnac, the mirrors were rotating because they were placed in the rotating platform.

On my example that we see here the mirrors are stationary on the surface of the Earth, meaning that the mirrors are not placed in one of the two rotating platforms where we have placed the blue and the green light source.

It makes no difference!!!

If we place the mirrors in one of the two rotating platforms where we have placed the blue and the green light source, it will not make any difference to the motion of the photons!!!

WHY???

Because the motion of the photons is not affected by the motion of the sources and also is not affected by the motion of the mirrors where the photons are reflecting!!!

The six photons that are emitted by the three sources (and forming two groups) will always make the same motion that they do now that the mirrors are stationary relative to the red light source!!!

The photons will always make the same motion that they do now, regardless of the motion of the mirrors or the motion of the sources!!!

The motion of the mirrors relative to the sources will not make any difference to the motion of the photons!!!

On the example that I have used here the mirrors are stationary relative to the red source.

If the mirrors are stationary relative to one of the other two sources it will not make any difference to the motion of the photons!!!

If for example we put the mirrors on the platform where the blue source is placed, and the mirrors are stationary relative to the blue source, it will not make any difference and the photons will make the same motion that they do now!!!

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As the motion of the photons continues and they keep reflecting to the mirrors, what will happen is that the **group of the photons A-B-C** will meet the **blue light source** before the **group of the photons D-E-F**, and the **group of the photons D-E-F** will meet the **green light source** before the **group of the photons A-B-C**(**figure 25**)!!!!

The two groups of photons will reach simultaneously the **red light source**(**figure 25**)!!!!

The **group of the photons A-B-C** will meet the **blue light source** before completing one circle, but the **group of the photons D-E-F** will reach the **blue light source** after completing more than one circle!!!

The **group of the photons D-E-F** will meet the **green light source** before completing one circle, but the **group of the photons A-B-C** will reach the **green light source** after completing more than one circle!!!

This is exactly the same with what has happened in the previous example(**figure 18**) where we were using balls instead of photons.

Let's focus on the photons that each source has emit.

The **red light source** has emit the **photons A & D**, and these photons will return to the source simultaneously.

The simultaneous return of the **photons A & D** to the **red light source** will produce a pattern of interference fringes on the source.

The **blue light source** has emit the **photons B & E**, and these photons will not return simultaneously to the source(**figure25**).

Due to the fact that the **photons B & E** will not return to the **blue source** simultaneously, the interference fringes on the blue light source will be shifted compared to the pattern of the interference fringes on the red light source!!!

The **green light source** has emit the **photons C & F**, and these photons will not return simultaneously to the source(**figure 25**).

Due to the fact that the **photons C & F** will not return to the **green source** simultaneously, the interference fringes on the green light source will be shifted compared to the pattern of the interference fringes on the red light source!!!

Figure 25. The two group of photons(A,B,C & D,E,F) are close to completing a circle.

Let's summarise.

We have two examples/experiments that leads us to the same conclusion!

We have one example/experiment with balls(**figures 15-16-17-18**) and another example/experiment with photons(**figures 22-23-24-25**), and on the two examples/ experiments we conclude that there is anisotropy of the one-way relative speed, between balls and their sources and between photons and their sources!!!

We cannot have different conclusions on the two cases!!!

What we see here on the examples where I have used rotational//revolutionary/circular motion(Sagnac experiment) and emission of photons or ejection of balls, is exactly the same with what we see in the previous examples in the **figures 5, 7 & 9** where there is linear motion and emission of photons and protons.

On the examples with rotational/revolutionary/circular motion(Sagnac experiment) we have two groups of photons, and sources that are in relative motion with each other, and of course only the one of the sources can be exactly between the two groups of photons and consequently have the same distance from the two groups of photons(**figures 23, 24-A, 24-B, 24-C**), meaning that for a source that does not have the same distance from the two groups of photons there is anisotropy of the one-way speed of light.

Exactly the same is what I describe on the examples(**figures 5, 7, 9**) where I have used linear motion.

On the examples(**figures 5, 7, 9**) where I have used linear motion, there are two groups of photons, and sources that are in relative motion with each other, and of course only the one of the sources can be exactly between the two groups of photons and consequently have the same distance from the two groups of photons, meaning that for the source that doesn't have the same distance from the two groups of photons there is anisotropy of the one-way speed of light!!!

In both situations, meaning linear motion or rotational/revolutionary/circular motion, the conclusions are the same, and the conclusions are that there is anisotropy of the one-way speed of light!!!!